

ON THE ISSUE OF COMPENSATING FOR THE LINEAR EXPANSION OF THE VIBRATORY CONVEYOR IN A DRYING EQUIPMENT

Drying of materials is one of the most common technological operations found in almost all industries. Currently there are a large number of different types of Drying equipment . For low-tonnage production the most promising is a drying unit where, as a working body for transportation with simultaneous drying, is used vibrating conveyor with directed vibrations and gas-distributing lattice in the form of louvers. In a general form, the vibrating conveyor has a conveying box mounted on elastic elements and equipped with a self-balancing vibration exciter. The box is divided into two parts by a gas distribution grid. In the lower part the coolant is supplied, in the upper part the material is transported. The disadvantage of this design scheme, due to the thermal expansion of the working chamber, is the displacement of the loading and unloading nozzles, which leads to misalignment of the elements of the joint assembly, which can reach tens of millimeters, and also the relative displacement of the attachment points of the compensation springs, which leads to their bending and, accordingly, bending and possible destruction of the working chamber. The disturbing force from the vibration exciter to the working chamber is mainly transmitted through the bracket placed in the middle of the working chamber, which leads to the appearance of bending vibrations of the working body.

Conducted laboratory studies have shown the possibility of eliminating the above-mentioned shortcomings in the creation of a vibratory conveyor (Fig. 1) with a modular-type working chamber.

The vibrating dryer consists of a number of modules 1 mounted on a single support frame 6 and rigidly connected to each other. Each module has two working chambers 2,3 movably connected to each other with the possibility of mutual longitudinal movement. The working chambers, in which the gas

distribution grate 4 is located, are fixed by brackets 7 and compensating springs 8 to the supporting frame 6 located on elastic elements 5 and equipped with a vibration exciter 9, loading 10 and unloading 11 units for docking with the bunker of initial 12 and finished 13 material.

Fig. 1

The connection of the working chambers 2,3 can be made by means of overhead strips 14 (Fig. 2a), shaped profile 15 (Fig. 2b), etc.

The vibration dryer operates as follows.

The material to be dried from the hopper 12, through the loading unit 10, is fed to the gas distribution grate 4 in a uniform layer across its entire width and begins to be transported to the unloading unit 11 under the action of directional vibrations created by the vibrating exciter 9.

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

During transportation, the material is dried in a vibro-boiling bed, which is formed by the influence of vibration and the coolant gas flow blown through the material.

The dried material is unloaded through the unit 11, into the hopper 13 or the transport line, and the exhaust coolant is removed to the atmosphere through the exhaust pipe 16, which can also be placed on any working chamber.

Depending on the drying conditions, the coolant has a wide temperature range, ranging from tens to hundreds of degrees. As a result of temperature exposure, undesirable deformation of the elements of the module's working chambers occurs, which can reach tens of millimeters.

With this design of the module 1, the working chambers 2; 3, expanding under the influence of temperature, have a counter displacement entering each other, which keeps the distance between the brackets 7 unchanged.

This also makes it possible to maintain (during thermal expansion) the distance (L) between the axis of the loading 10 and unloading 11 nodes unchanged, even with an unlimited number of modules. Accordingly, a predetermined alignment is maintained between the feedstock hopper 12 and the loading unit 10, and the finished material hopper 13 and the unloading unit 11.

This ensures the flow of the initial material in a given direction without destroying the mold, uniform filling of the gas distribution grate 4, achieving a uniform effect of the coolant on the material particle regardless of its physical and mechanical properties.

Compensating springs 8, when expanding the working chambers 2; 3, bend in the opposite direction (Fig. 3) by the same amount along the supporting frame 6. Being at a close distance from the attachment of the working boxes to the brackets 7, the springs 8 are deformed by a small amount, which practically eliminates the displacement of the working chambers and does not affect the rigidity of the structure.

Thus, the innovative design of the vibratory dryer allows, regardless of the temperature of the coolant, to compensate for the displacement of the connecting units of the vibratory dryer relative to stationary devices, which ensures a rational mode of exposure of the coolant to the material in a continuous transportation process and makes it possible to significantly increase the length of the developed vibratory dryers. The study of the experimental sample of the vibratory dryer showed its efficiency at high temperature heating and predetermined the program of further technological tests.